

Numerical investigation of the effects of compressibility on the flutter of a cantilevered plate in an inviscid, subsonic, open flow

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Abstract

We have carried out a numerical study of the influence of the upstream Mach number on the flutter of a two-dimensional, cantilevered, flexible plate subject to a subsonic, inviscid, open flow. We have assumed a linear elastic model for the plate and that the fluid flow is governed by the linearized potential theory. The fluid equations are solved with a novel frequency-domain, finite differences method to obtain the generalized aerodynamic forces as a function of the plate displacements. Then, these generalized forces are coupled to the equation of motion of the plate and an eigenvalue analysis is performed to find the flutter point. The obtained results are in good agreement with those of related theoretical and experimental studies found in the literature. To the best of our knowledge, the analysis performed here is the first self-consistent, parametric study of the influence of the compressibility on the flutter point of a two-dimensional cantilevered plate in subsonic flow.

Keywords: airfoil-fluid interaction, compressible subsonic flow, cantilevered plate, flutter, linearized potential flow, unsteady aerodynamics

1. Introduction

The flutter of a cantilevered plate is an example of fluid-structure interaction that has received great attention in the literature –e.g., in the monographs by Dowell [1] and Paidoussis [2]–, since it helps to understand many aeroelastic phenomena such as aircraft wing flutter [3], train panel flutter [4], energy harvesting [5, 6], human snoring [7] and paper web instability [8]. However, as we briefly review next, the major part of the results found in the literature are restricted to incompressible flows, whereas the effect of the compressibility –that may not be negligible in cases such as aircraft wing flutter or train panel flutter, among others– seems to have received little attention.

Such a lack of attention may be due to the fact that it is more difficult to obtain a direct relationship between aerodynamic loads over the plate and its motion when the flow is compressible. In effect, in the incompressible case, the numerical modelling of the flutter phenomenon has been traditionally approached by coupling the equation of motion of the plate to an appropriate aerodynamic model that provides the unsteady fluid pressures over the plate given its motion. Some of these aerodynamic models are based

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on theoretical relations [9, 10] obtained by Theodorsen [11] and Küssner and Schwartz [12] for unsteady, linearized, incompressible flows, as is done, for example, in the papers of Kornecki [13, 14], Huang [7], Guo and Païdoussis [15], Eloy et al. [16, 17], Li et al. [18–20] and Drazumeric et al. [21]. However, this procedure cannot be extended to linearized, compressible flows because, in this case, the relation between aerodynamic forces and the airfoil motion is governed by the more complicated Possio’s equation, for which no analytical solution is known, but only an approximated one [22].

Some other aerodynamic models are based on incompressible vortex-lattice methods, as happens in the works of Yamaguchi et al. [23], D. Tang et al. [3], Argentina and Mahadevan [24], L. Tang and Païdoussis [25, 26], L. Tang et al. [5, 27], Gibbs et al. [28], Zhao et al. [29], Howell and Lucey [30, 31], Alben [32], and Michelin and Llewellyn Smith [33]. Although these methods have been widely used in unsteady, incompressible aerodynamics –see, for example, [34]–, they present some inconveniences when extended to compressible flows [35, 36] such as: (i) they are based on a fundamental solution –the so-called *unsteady compressible vortex*– whose velocity field is not well-known and lacks a clear physical meaning [37], (ii) when formulated in the time domain, they have to keep track of the history of the vortices’ intensities in order to compute the pressure jumps at the airfoil at a given instant and (iii) their extension to three-dimensional flow is not clear, although some efforts have been done on the matter [38]. These drawbacks, which may also appear when using other kind of fundamental solutions, such as dipoles [39], or other boundary elements methods in general [40], considerably complicate the extension of the analysis of the incompressible flutter problem –usually performed using eigenvalue theory [30, 31] or time-domain simulations [3, 35, 36]– to the compressible case.

An alternative way to obtain the aerodynamic pressures over the plate given its motion is to directly solve the Navier-Stokes equations, as has been done by Watanabe et al. [8], Balint and Lucey [41], Khalili et al. [42] and Cisonni et al. [43]. Some of these authors [8, 42] have even considered compressibility effects for the case of very small Mach numbers, but their methods have proved to be too expensive compared to those based on potential flow theory [8]. Therefore, in order to deal with compressibility effects at higher Mach numbers, some investigators have tried an approach based on the direct discretization in space and in time of the linearized, compressible, potential flow equations. This is done, for example, in the works of Huang and Zhang [44] –who formulated a Chebyshev pseudospectral method– and of Colera and Pérez-Saborid [35, 36] –who employed finite differences–. However, only the latter authors effectively applied their method to compressible flows –since Huang and Zhang only considered the case of zero Mach number–. Finally, we should also mention the differential quadrature method developed by Li and Yang [4] to analyse the dynamics of panels wetted by one side in a compressible stream with the simplifying assumption that the incident flow remains unperturbed at the stations corresponding to the border of attack and to the trailing edge of the panel, respectively.

Compressibility effects on the flutter of a cantilevered, two-dimensional plate in a compressible, subsonic flow have been previously studied by Tanida [45] –who developed a compressible doublet-lattice method in the frequency domain for a plate in channel flow, but used only one Galerkin mode to describe its motion– and by Colera and Pérez-Saborid –who used first a compressible vortex-lattice method [37, 46, 47] and later a finite differences method [35, 36] to study a single case of a plate of given mass and stiffness–. The aim of this work is to generalize these investigations by performing a parametric study of the flutter speed and the flutter frequency of a two-dimensional, cantilevered plate in a compressible, subsonic flow as a function of its mechanical properties and the upstream Mach number. For that purpose, we have developed a numerical method based on expressing the plate equations of motion in terms of shape functions and generalized coordinates and on solving the equations for the linearized potential flow with a novel frequency-domain numerical scheme adapted from that presented in [35, 36].

The paper is structured as follows. First, the equations of motion of the plate are introduced in section 2. Then, a frequency-domain, finite differences method that provides the generalized aerodynamic forces is described and validated in section 3. The computation of the flutter curves of the plate is explained in section 4, whereas the results are discussed in section 5. Finally, some conclusions and future developments are pointed out in section 6.

2. Dynamic model of the plate

Consider the cantilevered flexible flat plate shown in figure 1. Let the incident flow –of density ρ_∞ , speed U_∞ and Mach number M_∞ – come in the x direction, along which the plate has a length L , and let the dimension along the z -axis, H , tend to infinity in order to simulate a two-dimensional problem in the x - y plane.

Figure 1: Scheme of a cantilevered flexible plate subject to an incident flow.

Since we are interested in computing just the flutter point of the plate, and not its post-critical (non-linear) behaviour, the linear, elastic, Kirchhoff's model can be used. In that case, the displacements of the mean line of the plate, $y_p(t, x)$, are governed by the equation [17]

$$\sigma \frac{\partial^2 y_p}{\partial t^2} + D \frac{\partial^4 y_p}{\partial x^4} = \Delta p, \quad (1)$$

where σ is the surface mass density, Δp is the pressure difference between the lower and the upper parts of the plate, and D is the flexural rigidity. The latter is given by $D = Eh_p^3/12/(1 - \nu^2)$, where E , h_p and ν are Young's modulus, the plate thickness and Poisson's coefficient, respectively.

The displacements of the mean line can be expressed by a Galerkin decomposition using the first m natural vibration modes *in vacuo*, $\psi_1(x), \dots, \psi_m(x)$, and their corresponding generalized coordinates, $q_1(t), \dots, q_m(t)$, as

$$y_p(t, x) = \sum_{i=1}^m \psi_i(x) q_i(t). \quad (2)$$

The natural modes are given by [48]

$$\psi_i(x) = \mathcal{C} \{ [\sin(\beta_i L) - \sinh(\beta_i L)] [\sin(\beta_i x) - \sinh(\beta_i x)] + \dots \\ [\cos(\beta_i L) + \cosh(\beta_i L)] [\cos(\beta_i x) - \cosh(\beta_i x)] \}, \quad (3)$$

where the parameters $\beta_1 < \beta_2 < \dots$ are the solutions of

$$\cos(\beta_i L) \cosh(\beta_i L) + 1 = 0,$$

and \mathcal{C} is a normalization constant so that

$$\int_0^L \psi_i^2 dx = L. \quad (4)$$

It can be shown that the natural modes verify

$$\frac{d^4 \psi_i}{dx^4} = \beta_i^4 \psi_i, \quad (5)$$

$$\int_0^L \psi_i \psi_j dx = 0 \quad (i \neq j). \quad (6)$$

Using now relations (2)-(6) in equation (1), we obtain

$$\sigma L \frac{\partial^2 q_i}{\partial t^2} + DL\beta_i^4 q_i = Q_i^{\text{aero}}, \quad i = 1, \dots, m, \quad (7)$$

where Q_i^{aero} are the aerodynamic generalized forces, computed as

$$Q_i^{\text{aero}}(t) = \int_0^L \Delta p(t, x) \psi_i(x) dx. \quad (8)$$

Since we are not interested in the transient response of the plate, but in its long-term behaviour, we seek solutions of the form

$$q_i(t) = \text{Re} [\tilde{q}_i \exp((n + j\omega)t)], \quad (9)$$

$$\Delta p(t, x) = \text{Re} [\Delta \tilde{p}(x) \exp((n + j\omega)t)],$$

$$Q_i^{\text{aero}}(t) = \text{Re} [\tilde{Q}_i^{\text{aero}} \exp((n + j\omega)t)]. \quad (10)$$

where j is the complex unit and n and ω are two real numbers that measure the damping ratio and the frequency of the motion. Then, equations (7) and (8) read as

$$[(n + j\omega)^2 \sigma L + DL\beta_i^4] \tilde{q}_i = \tilde{Q}_i^{\text{aero}}, \quad i = 1, \dots, m, \quad (11)$$

$$\tilde{Q}_i^{\text{aero}} = \int_0^L \Delta \tilde{p}(x) \psi_i(x) dx. \quad (12)$$

We will next derive a numerical, linear relation between the generalized coordinates and the generalized aerodynamic forces that will allow us to determinate the flutter point through equation (11).

3. Aerodynamic model

3.1. General unsteady equations

As with the elastic model, we use a linearized, small-perturbation theory [9, 10, 37, 49] to describe the (two-dimensional) aerodynamic flow past the plate. In this approximation, the thicknesses of the plate and of the wake are ignored and, independently of the kind of their small amplitude motion, they are assumed to be placed respectively on the intervals $0 \leq x \leq L$ and $L < x < \infty$ of the x-axis –i.e., at $y = 0^-$, which is parallel to the incident flow far from the plate (see figure 2), as commented before. The flow is non-viscous and irrotational in the rest of the domain, and hence it can be described by means of a velocity potential ϕ that verifies the convected wave equation at the fluid domain, i.e.,

$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + U_\infty \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \right)^2 \phi = a_\infty^2 \nabla^2 \phi, \quad (13)$$

being a_∞ the upstream sound speed. The boundary conditions are those of non-penetration at the plate's surface,

$$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial y_p}{\partial t} + U_\infty \frac{\partial y_p}{\partial x}, \quad 0 \leq x \leq L, \quad y = 0^+, \quad (14)$$

equilibrium of pressures at the wake –or generalized Kutta condition–,

$$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} + U_\infty \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x} = 0, \quad x > L, \quad y = 0^+, \quad (15)$$

and non-perturbed infinity,

$$\nabla \phi = 0, \quad x^2 + y^2 \rightarrow \infty. \quad (16)$$

124 It must be pointed out that the potential is antisymmetric with respect to the x axis and that it presents a
 125 finite jump discontinuity across the line $x > 0, y = 0$ (i.e., the region occupied by the plate and the wake).
 126 This potential jump is related to the pressure jump Δp between the lower and the upper parts of the plate
 127 by the relation

$$\Delta p = 2\rho_\infty \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + U_\infty \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \right) \phi^{\text{up}}(t, x),$$

128 where $\phi^{\text{up}}(t, x)$ denotes the potential at $y = 0^+$. Substituting the latter relation into (8) and integrating by
 129 parts, the generalized aerodynamic forces read as [35]

$$Q_i^{\text{aero}} = 2\rho_\infty \int_0^L \frac{\partial \phi^{\text{up}}}{\partial t} \psi_i dx + 2\rho_\infty U_\infty \psi_i(L) \phi^{\text{up}}(t, L) - 2\rho_\infty U_\infty \int_0^L \phi^{\text{up}} \frac{d\psi_i}{dx} dx. \quad (17)$$

Figure 2: (a) Scheme of a flexible plate in the sine of an uniform incident flow U_∞ and (b) simplification of the fluid flow made by the potential theory.

130 Using now (2) and writing $\phi(t, x, y)$ in the complex form

$$\phi(t, x, y) = \text{Re} \left[\tilde{\phi}(x, y) \exp((n + j\omega)t) \right],$$

131 as well as $q_i(t)$ and $Q_i^{\text{aero}}(t)$ (relations (9)-(10)), the equations (13)-(15),(17) read as

$$(a_\infty^2 - U_\infty^2) \frac{\partial^2 \tilde{\phi}}{\partial x^2} + a_\infty^2 \frac{\partial^2 \tilde{\phi}}{\partial y^2} - (n + j\omega)^2 \tilde{\phi} - 2U_\infty(n + j\omega) \frac{\partial \tilde{\phi}}{\partial x} = 0, \quad (18)$$

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{\phi}}{\partial y} = \sum_{i=1}^m \left[(n + j\omega) \psi_i + U_\infty \frac{d\psi_i}{dx} \right] \tilde{q}_i, \quad 0 \leq x \leq L, \quad y = 0^+, \quad (19)$$

$$(n + j\omega) \tilde{\phi} + U_\infty \frac{\partial \tilde{\phi}}{\partial x} = 0, \quad x > L, \quad y = 0^+, \quad (20)$$

$$\tilde{Q}_i^{\text{aero}} = 2\rho_\infty \int_0^L \left[(n + j\omega) \psi_i - U_\infty \frac{d\psi_i}{dx} dx \right] \tilde{\phi}^{\text{up}} dx + 2\rho_\infty U_\infty \psi_i(L) \tilde{\phi}^{\text{up}}(L) \quad (21)$$

135 3.2. Numerical discretization

136 The potential flow equations shown above are numerically solved by using an adaptation of a finite
 137 differences method presented first by Hariharan, Ping and Scott [50] and modified later by Colera and
 138 Pérez-Saborid [35, 36]. The adaptation consists in formulating the method in the frequency domain –
 139 equations (18)-(21)– instead of in the time domain –equations (13)-(17)–. This allows one to directly obtain
 140 the long-term behaviour of the plate without having to carry out a simulation until the end of the transient
 141 period (as done in [7, 36]) or without needing to compute the highest real part eigenvalue of the discretization
 142 matrix (as done in [4]), which saves a great computational cost.

143 Consider the rectangle shown in figure 3, whose dimensions are assumed to be large compared to the
 144 plate length (say of the order of 10L). The rectangle is located in the upper half plane, with the lower

145 side containing the plate and part of the wake, and is meshed into a non-uniform $N_x \times N_y$ grid with a
 146 larger density of points near the plate, since the latter is the focus of the convected waves described by
 147 equation (13) [37]. Every point of the grid, with coordinates (x_i, y_j) , will be defined by its indexes (i, j)
 148 –with $i = 1, \dots, N_x$ and $j = 1, \dots, N_y$ – or by a single, equivalent index I defined as

$$I = (j - 1)N_x + i, \quad (22)$$

149 and the phasor of the potential at that point will be denoted by $\tilde{\phi}_I$. The plate is placed between the points
 (0,0) and (L,0), whose corresponding indices I will be denoted by i_{le} and i_{te} , respectively.

Figure 3: Scheme of the grid employed for the modified Hariharan-Ping-Scott method.

150 It has to be pointed out that, since the computational domain is not infinite, equation (16) no longer
 151 applies and must be substituted by a non-reflecting boundary condition. The latter is derived in [35, 50]
 152 and, in complex form, reads as
 153

$$(n + j\omega)\tilde{\phi} + \dot{R}(\theta) \left[\frac{\partial \tilde{\phi}}{\partial x} \cos \theta + \frac{\partial \tilde{\phi}}{\partial y} \sin \theta + \frac{\tilde{\phi}}{2r} \right] = 0, \quad (23)$$

154 where

$$\dot{R}(\theta) = U_\infty \cos \theta + \sqrt{a_\infty^2 - U_\infty^2 \sin^2 \theta} \quad (24)$$

155 and (r, θ) are the polar coordinates in the x-y plane, defined so that $x = r \cos \theta$, $y = r \sin \theta$.

156 The potential flow equations (18)-(20),(23) are now discretized using non-equidistant finite differences,
 157 leading to the matricial relation

$$\mathbf{A}(U_\infty, a_\infty, n, \omega) \tilde{\boldsymbol{\phi}} = \mathbf{B}(U_\infty, n, \omega, \psi_1, \dots, \psi_m) \tilde{\mathbf{q}}, \quad (25)$$

158 where $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\phi}}$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{q}}$ are the column vectors

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\boldsymbol{\phi}} &= [\tilde{\phi}_1, \dots, \tilde{\phi}_{N_x N_y}]^T, \\ \tilde{\mathbf{q}} &= [\tilde{q}_1, \dots, \tilde{q}_m]^T, \end{aligned}$$

159 and \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} are two sparse matrices of dimensions $N_x N_y \times N_x N_y$ and $N_x N_y \times m$, respectively, whose
 160 elements are derived in Appendix A.

161 Note that (25) directly relates the values of the potential to those of the generalized coordinates describing
 162 the motion of the plate. At the same time, the potential is related to the generalized forces through equation
 163 (21). Indeed, discretizing the latter with the trapezoid rule and defining $\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}^{\text{aero}}$ as

$$\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}^{\text{aero}} = \left[\tilde{Q}_1^{\text{aero}}, \dots, \tilde{Q}_m^{\text{aero}} \right]^T,$$

164 we eventually arrive at

$$\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}^{\text{aero}} = \mathbf{C}(\rho_\infty, U_\infty, n, \omega, \psi_1, \dots, \psi_m) \tilde{\boldsymbol{\phi}},$$

165 where \mathbf{C} is a $m \times N_x N_y$ sparse matrix derived in Appendix A. The latter equation, combined with (25),
 166 gives the aimed relation between generalized aerodynamic forces and generalized coordinates:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}^{\text{aero}} = \mathbf{C} \cdot (\mathbf{A} \setminus \mathbf{B}) \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{q}}. \quad (26)$$

167 The notation $\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{A} \setminus \mathbf{B}$ (instead of $\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{A}^{-1} \mathbf{B}$) is a way to remark that we do not have to invert the matrix
 168 \mathbf{A} , but to solve the system $\mathbf{A} \mathbf{X} = \mathbf{B}$ with an appropriate method². In the present work, this task has been
 169 accomplished by using the `@Matlab's mldivide` command.

170 For what follows, it is convenient to rewrite (26) in the more compact form

$$\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}^{\text{aero}} = \boldsymbol{\Upsilon} \tilde{\mathbf{q}}, \quad (27)$$

171 where the $m \times m$ matrix $\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}$ is defined as

$$\boldsymbol{\Upsilon} = \boldsymbol{\Upsilon}(\rho_\infty, U_\infty, a_\infty, n, \omega, \psi_1, \dots, \psi_m) = \mathbf{C} \cdot (\mathbf{A} \setminus \mathbf{B}). \quad (28)$$

172 3.3. Validation of the aerodynamic model

173 In order to validate the aerodynamic model, we have considered both the damped and undamped os-
 174 cillatory motions of a rigid plate –characterized by two shape functions: $\psi_1(x) = 1$ and $\psi_2(x) = -x$ – and
 175 computed the evolution of the lift and the leading edge pitching moment (positive nose-up) coefficients along
 176 the time given some arbitrary initial conditions. The results obtained with the present method –valid for
 177 the permanent regime– have been compared to those obtained with (i) the modified Hariharan-Ping-Scott
 178 (HPS) time-domain, finite-differences method [35, 36, 50] and (ii) the Hernandez-Soviero (HS) time-domain,
 179 vortex-lattice method [37, 46, 47].

180 For the method presented in this work, we have always used a cartesian mesh of dimensions $N_x =$
 181 $151 \times N_y = 151$, limited by the lines $x = -10L$, $x = 10L$, $y = 0$ and $y = 10L$, and whose points have
 182 coordinates defined by

$$x_i = \begin{cases} -10L + 10L \sin\left(\frac{i-1}{N'_x} \frac{\pi}{2}\right), & i = 1, \dots, N'_x \\ \frac{L}{N'_x}(i - N'_x - 1), & i = N'_x + 1, \dots, 2N'_x + 1 \\ 10L - 9L \cos\left(\frac{i - 2N'_x + 1}{N'_x} \frac{\pi}{2}\right), & i = 2N'_x + 2, \dots, N_x \end{cases}$$

$$y_j = 10L - 10L \cos\left(\frac{j-1}{N_x-1} \frac{\pi}{2}\right), \quad j = 1, \dots, N_x$$

183 where $N'_x = (N_x - 1)/3$. Observe that the mesh has a larger density of points clustered near the plate.

184 The results obtained for three different Mach numbers –from low subsonic to almost supersonic– and
 185 three different values of the damping ratio n –negative, zero and positive– are plotted in figure 4. As can
 186 be seen, the results from the present method show excellent agreement in the permanent regime with those
 187 computed with the other two methods. Indeed, the absolute errors of the results are of the order of 10^{-3}
 188 with respect to those obtained with the modified HPS one, and of the order of 10^{-2} with respect to the
 189 results obtained with the HS method. Note that the frequency of the motion was chosen to be $3U_\infty/L$. This
 190 will be justified in section 5.1.

²This notation is clearly inspired in the `@Matlab's mldivide` command.

Figure 4: Evolution of the lift and the pitching coefficients (c_l and c_m , respectively) computed with different methods. The pitching moment is measured at the leading edge and is positive nose-up.

191 4. Computation of the flutter curves

192 In this section, we will compute the curves that provide the dependence of the flutter speed, U_f , and
 193 the flutter frequency, ω_f , on the parameters of the plate (σ, D, L) and the upstream density and Mach
 194 number. For that purpose, it is necessary to couple the relation (27) between the aerodynamic forces and
 195 the displacements of the plate to its equation of motion (11) to obtain the equation that describes the
 196 long-term dynamic response of the plate as

$$[(n + j\omega)^2 \mathbf{M}(\sigma, L) + \mathbf{K}(\sigma, D, L) - \mathbf{\Upsilon}(\rho_\infty, U_\infty, M_\infty, n, \omega)] \tilde{\mathbf{q}} = \mathbf{0}, \quad (29)$$

197 where \mathbf{M} and \mathbf{K} are the mass and stiffness matrices, defined as $(\mathbf{M})_{ij} = \sigma L \delta_{ij}$, $(\mathbf{K})_{ij} = DL \beta_i^4 \delta_{ij}$, being δ_{ij}
 198 the Kronecker delta³. For the sake of brevity, we will rewrite the latter equation as

$$\Theta(\rho_\infty, U_\infty, M_\infty, n, \omega, \sigma, D, L) \tilde{\mathbf{q}} = \mathbf{0}, \quad (30)$$

³Note that, in equation (29), $\mathbf{\Upsilon}$ has been written as a function of M_∞ , and not of a_∞ as in its definition (28), and that the dependence of $\mathbf{\Upsilon}$ on the shape functions has been omitted since these are fixed.

199 with $\Theta(\rho_\infty, U_\infty, M_\infty, n, \omega, \sigma, D, L) = (n + j\omega)^2 \mathbf{M}(\sigma, L) + \mathbf{K}(\sigma, D, L) - \Upsilon(\rho_\infty, U_\infty, M_\infty, n, \omega)$.

200 If the parameters of the plate are fixed, we have five unknowns at each point of the corresponding flutter
 201 curve: the aerodynamic variables ($\rho_\infty, U_\infty, M_\infty$), the damping ratio (n) and the frequency (ω). Two of
 202 the equations for their determination are obtained by imposing the non-triviality of the solution of equation
 203 (30), i.e., that the matrix Θ has null determinant or, equivalently, that its lowest magnitude eigenvector
 204 $\lambda_{min}(\Theta)$ is null. We found the latter condition, which reads as

$$\text{Re}[\lambda_{min}(\Theta)] = 0, \quad (31)$$

$$\text{Im}[\lambda_{min}(\Theta)] = 0, \quad (32)$$

205 to be numerically more stable. A third equation is obtained from the condition of marginal stability at the
 206 flutter point,

$$n = 0, \quad (33)$$

207 whereas the other two needed equations result, respectively, from the fact that we are interested in computing
 208 the flutter curves at constant Mach number, i.e.,

$$M_\infty = const., \quad (34)$$

209 and from the continuation method used for that purpose, which provides a relation that can be written in
 210 general form as

$$f(\rho_\infty, U_\infty, M_\infty, n, \omega, \rho_\infty^0, U_\infty^0, M_\infty^0, n^0, \omega^0) = 0, \quad (35)$$

211 being $(\rho_\infty^0, U_\infty^0, M_\infty^0, n^0, \omega^0)$ the coordinates of the last computed point of the curve. Equations (31)-(35)
 212 are then solved using the Broyden's "good" method [51, 52] to obtain different points of the flutter curve
 213 in a successive way. In all cases, we have used the first six Galerkin modes as shape functions, which are
 illustrated in figure 5.

Figure 5: First six *in vacuo* vibration modes used for the Galerkin decomposition.

214

215 5. Results and discussion

216 5.1. Flutter curves

217 Figure 6 shows the results obtained with the present method for the dependence of the dimensionless
 218 flutter speed U_f^* and of the dimensionless flutter frequency ω_f^* with the dimensionless density ρ^* , defined as

$$U_f^* = \sqrt{\frac{\sigma}{D}} L U_f, \quad \omega_f^* = \sqrt{\frac{\sigma}{D}} L^2 \omega_f, \quad \rho^* = \frac{\rho_\infty L}{\sigma},$$

219 for different upstream Mach numbers. It can be seen that, for low Mach numbers, the flutter speed presents
 220 two peaks at $\rho^* \simeq 1$ and $\rho^* \simeq 5$, whereas the flutter frequency presents two jumps at the same points.
 221 As the Mach number increases, those peaks and jumps become smoother, turning inappreciable for $M_\infty \gtrsim$
 222 0.85. Therefore, it seems that the compressibility of the air acts as some kind of mattress that affects the
 223 propagation of perturbations and makes the whole response of the system more uniform. The predicted
 224 flutter speed at $M_\infty = 0.01$ shows good agreement with that obtained by Eloy et al. [17] –also represented
 225 in the figure– for incompressible flow using a method developed by Kornecki et al. [13]. Observe in the
 226 figure that the flutter frequency is of the order of $3U_\infty/L$, as supposed in the model validation (section 3.3).

Figure 6: Dimensionless flutter speed and frequency as a function of the dimensionless density for various Mach numbers.

227 It is interesting to note that, for $\rho^* \gtrsim 0.4$, the flutter speed curves corresponding to $M_\infty = 0.01$ and to
 228 $M_\infty = 0.2$ almost overlap into a single one. However, for $\rho^* \lesssim 0.4$, the flutter speed for $M_\infty = 0.2$ is about
 229 a 5-15% higher than that for $M_\infty = 0.01$. Thus, experimental measurements of the flutter speed (typically
 230 performed at $M_\infty \simeq 0.1$) for low values of ρ^* could overestimate the flutter speed in comparison with an
 231 incompressible theory due to the compressibility effects. The corresponding flutter frequencies, on the other
 232 hand, keep below a 5% of discrepancy, being the lowest that corresponding to $M_\infty = 0.2$. These aspects
 233 have been illustrated in figure 7.

235 The amplitude of the different generalized coordinates (with respect to $|\tilde{q}_1|$) is represented in figure 8.
 236 There, it can be seen that, for low Mach numbers, the different Galerkin modes seem to intensify their
 237 participation at some interval(s) of ρ^* placed before/after $\rho^* \simeq 1$ and $\rho^* \simeq 5$. In particular, the highest
 238 (lowest) Galerkin modes become more important at high (low) densities. This may be due to the fact that
 239 the aerodynamic forces are proportional to the density, somehow making the system more rigid and exciting
 240 higher vibration modes when the density increases. For high Mach numbers, however, the participations of
 241 the different modes increase monotonically with the density. This may indicate that, as in the case of U_f^*
 242 and ω_f^* , the air compressibility tends to avoid sudden changes in the dependence of the modal amplitudes
 243 with respect to ρ^* . In addition, it can be seen that the amplitude of the first Galerkin mode turns out to
 244 be the highest when the Mach number increases, especially at high Mach numbers $M_\infty \gtrsim 0.85$.

245 The behaviors observed in figure 8 are closely related to the dependence of the flutter frequency with the
 246 density observed in figure 6, since it can be seen that the amplitudes of the higher modes correspondingly
 247 increase with higher flutter frequencies. Thus, the jumps that the different $|\tilde{q}_i|/|\tilde{q}_1|$ present at low Mach
 248 numbers are related to corresponding jumps in the flutter frequency, the latter being higher for larger

Figure 7: Dimensionless flutter speed and frequency as a function of the Mach number for low values of ρ^* .

Figure 8: Amplitudes of the Galerkin modes at flutter with respect to $|\tilde{q}_1|$.

densities, as pointed out above. For larger Mach numbers, the amplitudes $|\tilde{q}_i|/|\tilde{q}_1|$ increase smoothly with the density, as does the flutter frequency. In addition, it can be checked through figure 8 that the amplitudes of the modes, $|\tilde{q}_i|$, decrease with i , and also that $|\tilde{q}_6|/|\tilde{q}_1| \leq 0.035 \ll 1$. This confirms us that the six Galerkin modes used in this work are enough to provide a reliable computation of the results. Nevertheless, the effect of the number of modes on the solution will be discussed in section 5.2.

In all the above mentioned figures, it can be seen that effect of the compressibility is more accused for Mach numbers in the range from 0.6 to 0.8, where the curves present the strongest qualitative changes. By contrast, the curves corresponding to Mach numbers from 0.01 to 0.2 seem to be almost identical—something expectable since, in that, range, the fluid can be considered incompressible—, and the same happens to those corresponding to Mach numbers from 0.8 to 0.99.

The flutter modes obtained by the present method for $\rho^* = 0.74$ and $\rho^* = 1.94$, as well as those obtained experimentally by Eloy et al. [17] for incompressible flow, are plotted in figures 10 and 11. It can be observed that, as expected from figure 8, the flutter mode is similar to a combination of the first two natural modes for low Mach numbers and $\rho^* = 0.74$, whereas for low Mach numbers and $\rho^* = 1.94$, it looks more similar to a combination of the first three modes. The flutter mode for low Mach numbers and $\rho^* = 0.74$ is also in accordance with other experimental studies for close values of ρ^* [53]. Finally, for both values of ρ^* and high Mach numbers, the flutter mode looks similar to the first one.

In order to check the obtained results, the dimensionless flutter speed is plotted in figure 9 as a function of the upstream Mach number for $\rho^* = 0.6$ and compared to that obtained by Colera and Pérez-Saborid [35–37] by two different time-domain methods: the modified HPS [35, 36] and the HS [46, 47] methods. As can be seen, the agreement between the results of these methods is very good, except for the HS method, which does not provide the incompressible solution at $M_\infty \rightarrow 0$.

Figure 9: Dimensionless flutter speed as a function of the upstream Mach number.

We strongly emphasize that the results for Mach numbers above $\simeq 0.8$ must be considered with care, since the flow may be transonic at this range and thus it should not be studied with the linearized theory used in the present work. Nevertheless, they can still be useful for a first qualitative understanding of the phenomenon or for validation and comparison of results in future works. In addition, when the flow speed is above the flutter one and thus the plate oscillations increase in amplitude, the assumption of small displacements made in the linear elastic and aerodynamic models is no longer valid. In those cases, nonlinear effects and chaos may appear, and must be taken into account to study the post-critical behaviour of the plate [18, 20, 25].

Figure 10: Flutter modes for $\rho^* = 0.74$: experimental results from Eloy et al. [17] for incompressible flow (upper left) and numerical results for different Mach numbers obtained with the present method (rest of figures).

Figure 11: Flutter modes for $\rho^* = 1.94$: experimental results from Eloy et al. [17] for incompressible flow (upper left) and numerical results for different Mach numbers obtained with the present method (rest of figures).

5.2. Dependence of the flutter solution on the number of modes and on the grid

As said in section 4, we have used the first six *in vacuo* modes as shape functions, and a 151×151 grid covering the $[-10L, 10L] \times [0, 10L]$ rectangle. However, in order to check that these choices were appropriate, we have also studied the influence of the number of modes and of the grid size and density on the flutter solution of two particular cases: (i) $\rho^* = 5$ and $M_\infty = 0.01$, near which the last mode takes its greatest participation –see figure 8– and thus the results can be expected to be less accurate than in any other case, and (ii) $\rho^* = 1$ and $M_\infty = 0.5$, which corresponds to a more typical case.

Figure 12 shows the flutter speed and frequency as a function of the number of modes. As can be seen, the inclusion of more than six modes does not appreciably change the results –those are below the 0.5% relative to the final value–, but results in a slightly higher computational cost. Thus, six modes can be considered sufficient to capture the flutter solution.

Figure 12: Convergence of U_f^* and ω_f^* with the number of modes. $(\cdot)_{\text{sol}}$ denotes the value corresponding to six modes.

On the other hand, the results computed for a rectangle of the form $[-l, l] \times [0, l]$ are shown, as a function of l , in figure 13. In all cases, the number of grid points at the plate was kept to 51. However, the number of grid points before and after the plate and the number of points along the y -axis were varied so that the density of points remained constant. As can be seen, increasing the rectangle length above $l = 10L$ does not make the results vary more than a 0.1% relative. Note that, for the cases considered in the figure, the results are also good for sizes lower than $l = 10L$. However, this may not always happen with the modified HPS method, as shown in [35]. In general, since the non-reflecting boundary condition (23) is an asymptotic approximation of the far field solution of the wave equation [50], it is necessary to keep the left, upper and right limits of the domain far enough from the source of the waves –the plate–, i.e., at a distance $\simeq 10L$ from it.

Finally, figure 14 shows the effect on the flutter solution of the number of grid points. In all cases, the domain was fixed to the original $[-10L, 10L] \times [0, 10L]$ rectangle, and the grid was constructed with N_p points before the plate, $N_p + 1$ points at the plate, N_p points after the plate, and $3N_p + 1$ points along the y -axis, being N_p a parameter. As can be seen, when N_p is above 50, results vary less than a 1% relative. Since the computational cost increases greatly with N_p , a choice of $N_p = 50$ could be considered appropriate for our case.

5.3. Frequency domain analysis vs. time domain one

Apart from providing an understanding of the flutter behavior of the cantilevered plate with the Mach number and other parameters, the obtained results can enlighten the convenience of using a frequency domain analysis instead of a time domain one for this problem in particular.

The main advantage of the frequency-domain formulation is the amount of computational cost that can be saved respect to a time-domain one. Indeed, although we have discretized the potential flow equations

Figure 13: Convergence of U_f^* and ω_f^* with the number of modes. $(\cdot)_{\text{sol}}$ denotes the value corresponding to $l = 10L$.

Figure 14: Convergence of U_f^* and ω_f^* with the number of modes. $(\cdot)_{\text{sol}}$ denotes the value corresponding to $N_p = 50$.

312 in a 151×151 grid, it is possible to obtain a final relation between aerodynamic forces and displacements of
 313 the form $\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}^{\text{aero}} = \mathbf{\Upsilon} \tilde{\mathbf{q}}$ —see equation (27)—, being $\mathbf{\Upsilon}$ an $m \times m$ matrix, and being m a small number ($m = 6$
 314 in this work). The computation of $\mathbf{\Upsilon}$ is the most expensive task when attempting to compute a flutter point
 315 of the curve, since it requires the creation of the big (sparse) matrices related to the aerodynamic model and
 316 the resolution of the system (28) formed by those, but this task that is relatively quickly performed, e.g., in
 317 $\simeq 1s$ with an @Intel Core 2 Duo, as in this work. After $\mathbf{\Upsilon}$, one has to compute the lowest eigenvalue of $\mathbf{\Theta}$,
 318 but the latter is a small $m \times m$ matrix and thus this operation does not take an appreciable time.

319 However, when using a time domain method and a compressible flow formulation, the aerodynamic forces
 320 must be expressed as a function of the whole previous history of the plate—this happens, typically, when
 321 coupling the fluid dynamic loads to the plate dynamics with a boundary elements method, as in [37]— or as a
 322 function of the generalized coordinates and the potential at the fluid domain—as happens when discretizing
 323 the potential, compressible flow equations, as in [4, 35, 36]—. Then, when attempting to compute a flutter
 324 point of the curve, one has to solve an eigenvalue problem [4] with a matrix that is not $m \times m$ now, but
 325 much bigger, since it corresponds to the spatial discretization of the potential flow equations, or to perform
 326 a simulation until the transient disappears [7, 35, 36]. Any of those operations is far more expensive than
 327 computing the above mentioned matrix $\mathbf{\Upsilon}$, and thus the frequency domain method turns out to be more
 328 efficient.

6. Conclusions

In the present work, we have computed the flutter speed and the flutter frequency of a two-dimensional cantilevered flexible plate as functions of the density and the Mach number of the incident flow and of the mass, the length and the stiffness of the plate. For that purpose, we have expressed the dynamic equations of the plate in terms of Galerkin modes and approached the resolution of the potential flow equations with a novel numerical scheme similar to that presented in [35, 36, 50], but which has been formulated here in the frequency domain instead of in the time domain. The efficiency of the proposed method relies on writing the discretized equations of the airfoil-fluid system in such a way that only eigenvalues of a matrix whose size is determined by the number of the structural degrees of freedom need to be computed.

Although in this work the method has been applied only to the case of a cantilevered plate, it has been implemented in such a way that is valid for any two-dimensional, flexible plate with a linear equation of motion. Our results are in good agreement with the experimental and numerical results obtained by Eloy et al. [17] for incompressible flow, and also with those computed numerically by Colera and Pérez-Saborid [35, 36] for a compressible flow of fixed dimensionless density ρ^* . To the best of our knowledge, this is the first parametric study carried out in the literature about the flutter of a two-dimensional, flexible, cantilevered plate subject to a compressible, subsonic flow.

The results show that the effect of the air compressibility is to reduce the intensity of the peaks and jumps that both the flutter speed and the flutter frequency experience when the density increases. Indeed, for Mach numbers above $\simeq 0.85$ –and assuming that no transonic behavior takes place in this range– those peaks and jumps apparently disappear. Another interesting conclusion is that, for low values of ρ^* , experimental measurements –performed typically at $M_\infty \simeq 0.1$ – could overestimate about a 5% the flutter speed respect to the incompressible theory due to compressibility effects.

The air compressibility also affects the way in which the individual Galerkin components participate in the flutter mode as the dimensionless density varies. For Mach numbers below $M_\infty \simeq 0.85$, the amplitudes of the different generalized coordinates change in a relatively abrupt way at certain values of ρ^* . These jumps appear at lower (higher) dimensionless densities when the corresponding generalized coordinates are those associated with the lowest (highest) Galerkin modes. Thus, it seems that higher densities imply higher Galerkin modes –and hence higher frequencies– being excited. However, for Mach numbers above $M_\infty \simeq 0.85$, the amplitudes in the flutter mode of the different generalized coordinates increase monotonically with ρ^* without presenting any kind of jumps. Another remarkable point is that, when the Mach number increases, the first Galerkin mode becomes the one with the highest amplitude.

Of course, the aforementioned facts affect to the shape of the flutter modes. For Mach numbers below $M_\infty \simeq 0.85$, the flutter modes may be a combination of several Galerkin modes, depending on the dimensionless density. However, for $M_\infty \gtrsim 0.85$, the flutter mode looks more similar to the first Galerkin mode, and the influence of other Galerkin modes may only be important for dimensionless densities close to 10.

The main changes in the qualitative behavior of the different variables have been found to occur from $M_\infty \simeq 0.6$ to $M_\infty \simeq 0.8$. Above and below that range, all the graphs look very similar, especially for Mach numbers below 0.2 –which is expectable, since this range belongs to the incompressible regime– and for Mach numbers above $\simeq 0.8$.

We hope that our work may provide some insight about the influence of the compressibility in the flutter of a cantilevered, two-dimensional plate subject to subsonic, open flow. We also expect that the numerical method developed here be useful for researchers in the field of aeroelasticity interested in studying the effect of the compressibility on the flutter point of other configurations –e.g., clamped-clamped, clamped-free, cantilevered-attached to a spring, etc.–. Some tasks could be addressed in the future, such as the inclusion of structural damping in the mechanical model, the study of the effect of attaching the plate to a string, the implementation of a compact finite differences scheme in the aerodynamic model to achieve more accuracy and efficiency, and the extension of the analysis to nonlinear flow.

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379 **Appendix A. Matrices A, B, and C**

380 In order to write the discretization of the potential flow equations (18)-(20),(23) in a non-uniform mesh
 381 in a more comfortable way, we will adopt the following notation: if $(x_{i_1}, f_{i_1}), \dots, (x_{i_N}, f_{i_N})$ is a set of N
 382 interpolation points of a function $f(x)$, the approximations for the first and second derivatives of f at a
 383 node x_i ($i_1 \leq i \leq i_N$) will be written as

$$f'(x_i) \simeq \sum_{l=l_1}^{l_N} (\alpha'_{l_1, \dots, l_N})_i^l f_{i+l}, \quad f''(x_i) \simeq \sum_{l=l_1}^{l_N} (\alpha''_{l_1, \dots, l_N})_i^l f_{i+l},$$

384 where $l_1 = i_1 - i, \dots, l_N = i_N - i$. Note that the sub-index i and the super-index l in the latter coefficients
 385 denote the influence of f_{i+l} –and not of f_l – on $f'(x_i)$ or $f''(x_i)$. At the same time, the sub-index l_1, \dots, l_N
 386 (with $l_1 < \dots < l_N$) is used to indicate the number of points used for the formula and their relative location
 387 to x_i –e.g., $l_1 < l_N = 0$ for a backward formula and $0 = l_1 < l_N$ for a forward one–. The values of the
 388 derivation weights can be obtained by taking derivatives in the Lagrange interpolants, which provides

$$\begin{aligned} (\alpha'_{l_1, \dots, l_N})_i^l &= \frac{1}{\prod_{m \neq l} (x_{i+l} - x_{i+m})} \sum_{m \neq l} \prod_{n \neq l, m} (x_{i+l} - x_{i+n}), \\ (\alpha''_{l_1, \dots, l_N})_i^l &= \frac{1}{\prod_{m \neq l} (x_{i+l} - x_{i+m})} \sum_{m \neq l} \sum_{n \neq l, m} \prod_{p \neq l, m, n} (x_{i+l} - x_{i+p}), \end{aligned}$$

389 where the indexes m, n, p used for the summations and products take the values l_1, \dots, l_N . In order to avoid
 390 confusions, the weight coefficients of the derivatives with respect to y will be denoted with the symbol β
 391 instead of α .

392 Note that, if a point of the mesh is denoted by the single index I –equation (22)–, then the indexes that
 393 correspond to the points just at the right, left, up and down are $I+1, I-1, I+N_x$ and $I-N_x$, respectively.

394 Taking this into account, we can proceed now to discretize the potential flow equations (18)-(20),(23) in
 395 the different parts of the fluid domain as follows:

396 *Inner points.* At the inner points of the grid, the convected wave equation (18) is discretized by using a
 397 two-point upwind formula for the first derivative respect to x –which results in a more stable scheme than
 398 using a central one [50]– and three-point central formulas for the second derivatives. This provides the
 399 following non-zero terms of \mathbf{A} :

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathbf{A})_{I,I} &= (a_\infty^2 - U_\infty^2) (\alpha''_{-1,0,1})_I^0 + a_\infty^2 (\beta''_{-N_x,0,N_x})_I^0 - 2U_\infty (n + j\omega) (\alpha'_{-1,0})_I^0 - (n + j\omega)^2, \\ (\mathbf{A})_{I,I-1} &= (a_\infty^2 - U_\infty^2) (\alpha''_{-1,0,1})_I^{-1} - 2U_\infty (n + j\omega) (\alpha'_{-1,0})_I^{-1}, \\ (\mathbf{A})_{I,I+1} &= (a_\infty^2 - U_\infty^2) (\alpha''_{-1,0,1})_I^1, \\ (\mathbf{A})_{I,I-N_x} &= a_\infty^2 (\beta''_{-N_x,0,N_x})_I^{-N_x}, \\ (\mathbf{A})_{I,I+N_x} &= a_\infty^2 (\beta''_{-N_x,0,N_x})_I^{N_x}, \end{aligned}$$

400 where I corresponds to an inner point.

401 *Left, upper and right boundaries.* At the boundaries, we use three-point formulas (central if possible, back-
 402 ward or forward otherwise, depending on the boundary) for discretizing the derivatives at the non-reflecting
 403 condition (23), obtaining the following non-zeros of **A**:

$$\begin{aligned}(\mathbf{A})_{I,I} &= (n + j\omega) + \dot{R}_I \left((\alpha'_{0,1,2})_I^0 \cos \theta_I + (\beta'_{-N_x,0,N_x})_I^0 \sin \theta_I + \frac{1}{2r_I} \right), \\(\mathbf{A})_{I,I+1} &= \dot{R}_I (\alpha'_{0,1,2})_I^1 \cos \theta_I, \\(\mathbf{A})_{I,I+2} &= \dot{R}_I (\alpha'_{0,1,2})_I^2 \cos \theta_I, \\(\mathbf{A})_{I,I-N_x} &= \dot{R}_I (\beta'_{-N_x,0,N_x})_I^{-N_x} \sin \theta_I, \\(\mathbf{A})_{I,I+N_x} &= \dot{R}_I (\beta'_{-N_x,0,N_x})_I^{N_x} \sin \theta_I,\end{aligned}$$

404 for I belonging to a point of the left boundary,

$$\begin{aligned}(\mathbf{A})_{I,I} &= (n + j\omega) + \dot{R}_I \left((\alpha'_{-1,0,1})_I^0 \cos \theta_I + (\beta'_{-2N_x,-N_x,0})_I^0 \sin \theta_I + \frac{1}{2r_I} \right), \\(\mathbf{A})_{I,I-1} &= \dot{R}_I (\alpha'_{-1,0,1})_I^{-1} \cos \theta_I, \\(\mathbf{A})_{I,I+1} &= \dot{R}_I (\alpha'_{-1,0,1})_I^1 \cos \theta_I, \\(\mathbf{A})_{I,I-N_x} &= \dot{R}_I (\beta'_{-2N_x,-N_x,0})_I^{-N_x} \sin \theta_I, \\(\mathbf{A})_{I,I-2N_x} &= \dot{R}_I (\beta'_{-2N_x,-N_x,0})_I^{-2N_x} \sin \theta_I,\end{aligned}$$

405 for I corresponding to a point in the upper boundary, and

$$\begin{aligned}(\mathbf{A})_{I,I} &= (n + j\omega) + \dot{R}_I \left((\alpha'_{-2,-1,0})_I^0 \cos \theta_I + (\beta'_{-N_x,0,N_x})_I^0 \sin \theta_I + \frac{1}{2r_I} \right), \\(\mathbf{A})_{I,I-1} &= \dot{R}_I (\alpha'_{-2,-1,0})_I^{-1} \cos \theta_I, \\(\mathbf{A})_{I,I-2} &= \dot{R}_I (\alpha'_{-2,-1,0})_I^{-2} \cos \theta_I, \\(\mathbf{A})_{I,I-N_x} &= \dot{R}_I (\beta'_{-N_x,0,N_x})_I^{-N_x} \sin \theta_I, \\(\mathbf{A})_{I,I+N_x} &= \dot{R}_I (\beta'_{-N_x,0,N_x})_I^{N_x} \sin \theta_I,\end{aligned}$$

406 when I represents a point of the right boundary. In the latter equations, r_I , θ_I and \dot{R}_I are, respectively,
 407 the corresponding values of r , θ and \dot{R} –defined in section 3.1– at the point (x_I, y_I) . On the other hand, we
 408 impose at the corners that the potential has the mean value of the two adjacent points, that is,

$$\begin{aligned}(\mathbf{A})_{I,I} &= 1, \\(\mathbf{A})_{I,I-N_x} = (\mathbf{A})_{I,I+1} &= -0.5\end{aligned}$$

409 for I belonging to the upper left corner, and

$$\begin{aligned}(\mathbf{A})_{I,I} &= 1, \\(\mathbf{A})_{I,I-1} = (\mathbf{A})_{I,I-N_x} &= -0.5\end{aligned}$$

410 for I corresponding to the upper right corner.

411 *Plate.* At the points belonging to the plate, we discretize the derivatives of the potential in the non-
412 penetration condition (19) with a three-point forward formula, which provides

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathbf{A})_{I,I} &= (\beta'_{0,N_x,2N_x})_I^0, \\ (\mathbf{A})_{I,I+N_x} &= (\beta'_{0,N_x,2N_x})_I^{N_x}, \\ (\mathbf{A})_{I,I+2N_x} &= (\beta'_{0,N_x,2N_x})_I^{2N_x}, \\ (\mathbf{B})_{I,J} &= (n + j\omega) \psi_J(x_I) + U_\infty \frac{d\psi_J}{dx}(x_I) \end{aligned}$$

413 with I representing a point of the plate and with $J = 1, \dots, m$.

414 *Wake.* The Kutta condition is discretized using a two-point upwind formula for the derivative of the potential
415 respect to x , yielding

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathbf{A})_{I,I} &= (n + j\omega) + U_\infty (\alpha'_{-1,0})_I^0, \\ (\mathbf{A})_{I,I-1} &= (n + j\omega) + U_\infty (\alpha'_{-1,0})_I^{-1}, \end{aligned}$$

416 for I corresponding to a point of the wake.

417 *Lower boundary up to the airfoil.* Since the potential is antisymmetric and continuous at $x \leq 0, y = 0$, we
418 have

$$(\mathbf{A})_{I,I} = 1$$

419 where the point denoted by I belongs to the lower boundary before the airfoil.

420 Finally, if we define

$$(\Delta x)_I = \begin{cases} x_{I+1} - x_I, & I = i_{le} \\ x_{I+1} - x_{I-1}, & I = i_{le} + 1, \dots, i_{te} - 1 \\ x_I - x_{I-1}, & I = i_{te} \end{cases}$$

421 and apply the trapezoidal rule to the RHS of (21), we eventually arrive at the following expression for the
422 matrix **C** that relates the generalized aerodynamic forces to the values of the potential:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{C} &= \rho_\infty (n + j\omega) \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \dots & i_{le} & \dots & i_{te} & \dots & N_x N_y \\ 0 & 0 & (\Delta x)_{i_{le}} \psi_1(x_{i_{le}}) & \dots & (\Delta x)_{i_{te}} \psi_1(x_{i_{te}}) & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & (\Delta x)_{i_{le}} \psi_m(x_{i_{le}}) & \dots & (\Delta x)_{i_{te}} \psi_m(x_{i_{te}}) & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} + \\ &+ \rho_\infty U_\infty \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \dots & i_{le} & \dots & i_{te} & \dots & N_x N_y \\ 0 & 0 & (\Delta x)_{i_{le}} \psi'_1(x_{i_{le}}) & \dots & (\Delta x)_{i_{te}} \psi'_1(x_{i_{te}}) & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & (\Delta x)_{i_{le}} \psi'_m(x_{i_{le}}) & \dots & (\Delta x)_{i_{te}} \psi'_m(x_{i_{te}}) & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} + \\ &+ 2\rho_\infty U_\infty \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \dots & i_{te} & \dots & N_x N_y \\ 0 & 0 & \psi_1(L) & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \psi_m(L) & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}. \end{aligned}$$

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